

INVESTIGATIVE STUDY OF ARCHAEO-METALLURGY OF KATSINA STATE

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ABSTRACT

This project studied both historical as well as metallurgical aspect of metal working. It compared the ancient metallurgical technology of Katsina state with modern ones; its development and collapse of the industry. Some metallurgical examinations and tests were carried out on some of the blacksmiths to assess the level of development attained by these practices. Based on the study carried out, ways of improvement were suggested.

KEYWORDS: Archeometallurgy, Katsina State, Blacksmiths, Primitive Furnaces, Smelting, Smithing.

INTRODUCTION

Iron smelting in Hausaland predated the Jihad of 1804. Available evidence indicated that Katsina zone of Hausaland, where iron working has been going on for over 1000 years (Okafor, 1997), was the most active in this activity. This is because of the abundant iron ore deposits found in most parts of this area. Notable in this area are Pauwa, Katsina and Lafiaro, where the ore deposits are found in stony lands.

The introduction of steel during the colonial era put a halt to iron mining and smelting, and was in fact completely abandoned, with a very few of the miners and smelters turning to blacksmiths.

The two most common ways of detecting the presence of the ore by the local miners were by noticing its presence on the earth's surface and by noticing the ore's particle-heaps deposited by ants around their habitats. The ore was then mined (usually by a group of miners and always during the dry season) by digging a trench to the depth at which the ore deposit was met. The mined ore was then transported to the area designated for smelting, usually where there was abundant presence of water, wood and grass.

The smelting operation comprised of building a furnace, which is a granary-like structure made of fine clay and which usually took about ten days (including the drying period). Meanwhile, a ditch, about 20 ft deep was dug and filled with grasses. Next, about four nozzles (Tuyeres) were built around the ditch. The furnace was then placed over the ditch and nozzles. Next, about five baskets of charcoal were placed inside the furnace, followed by about nineteen baskets of the raw ore, on top of which substantial logs of hard wood were placed. Fire was then made and allowed to burn until the ore smelted into iron. This took between 30 and 36 hours. Normally, the slog product soaked away into the ground through the grasses. The resulting pig iron took 2 to 3 days to completely cool before it was removed.

The pig iron was then sold to the blacksmiths who then used it to manufacture such iron wares as locks, guns, hoe blades, etc.

This work is aimed at studying the ancient iron working processes in Katsina state of Nigeria, from ore mining stage through the smelting to the smithing stages. These processes would then be compared with the modern methods and ways of improving the ancient one suggested.

Table 1: Comparison of the primitive furnace with the modern blast furnace.

Primitive Furnace	Modern (Blast) Furnace
The height of the primitive furnace was not more than 2m, and the diameter was about 0.5m at the top and 2m at the bottom.	The height of the blast furnace is about 20m or more from the bottom to the top of the furnace.
Made of clay mixed with grasses.	Generally made of thick steel shell lined with refractory bricks on the inside.
Charcoal used as fuel.	Coke used as fuel.
The maximum temperature attained by any means did not exceed 1000°C and as such only the slag could be melted while the spongy iron formed bloom.	Can attain up to 2000°C and as such both the slag and iron can be melted as the melting point of iron is 1500°.
Each furnace was capable of smelting at most only about 0.3 tons of iron at a time and could be done in 30 to 36 hours.	Capable of producing substantial amount of iron on hourly basis, with the furnace operating for several years nonstop.
During smelting operation, special sand was used as flux which gave the slag some suitable composition.	Calcium carbonate or limonite is used as flux and the slag has suitable composition in iron reduction.
Had between 4 to 5 tuyeres and were bellows-driven and forced draught.	Has as many tuyeres as possible, depending on the capacity of the blast furnace and the tuyeres are forced draught.
A single furnace could only be used for smelting four times at the most after which it was discarded for a new one.	Once it is in use, it can be in operation for many years without shut down.

HISTORICAL BACKGROUND AND ARCHEOLOGICAL EVIDENCE

The earliest known occurrence of iron smelting in tropical Africa comes from Taruga (southern Kaduna, Nigeria) and dated back to 400 BC. Evidence of the development of iron technology in Africa comes from two sources: archeology and ethnography [Andah, 1997].

In Katsina state, there are many iron smelting sites [Okafor, 1997], including Katsina, Lafiara, Daura, Kankara (Pauwa) and Tama, where many slag blocks, fragments of clay nozzles (tuyeres), baked red mud walls of furnaces, and other industrial debris could still be found today. In fact, the significant role played by the Kankara region in iron working is seen by some writers as the main iron production centre in the whole of Hausaland.

Katsina smiths have been involved for many centuries in the manufacture of essential metal ware products for both local consumption and for sale outside the region. The production, organization, distribution, and exchange of these goods involved, at different stages, miners, smelters, dealers, traders from far and near, the smiths, and the commission agents.

The smiths, as a rule, did not smelt or mine ores, which are normally done by professional ore miners and smelters. The smiths from rural areas would travel around the various mining camps to buy iron for themselves and for other smiths back home. The blacksmiths who were skilled enough to mine and smelt their own ore would first have to sought permission from their chief in the area.

Perfection of skills which lead to very high skills was enhanced by the exchange of ideas between industrialists from other areas like Kano, Sokoto, and Zamfara who converged at these areas like Pauwa for production and manufacture of iron wares.

There were also skills specializations by different groups dating back from the pre-colonial era. This is evidenced by the fact that smiths from Gwangwan and Kofar Kaura wards specialized in such horse-riding equipment as stirrups and swords; those from Kofar Keke in swords; Saulawa in manufacture of door locks; and those from Masanawa in agricultural implements like ploughs, hoes and axes. The skills were so perfected that hardly did the key to one lock unlocks another, for example.

Though smithing was basically a family profession that was passed down from generation to generation of the family, apprenticeship, involving others with no smithing background, was also practiced. The apprentice did not pay tuition and could come and go as he pleased.

Table 2: Chemical constituent of slag from bloomery iron smelting

Constituent	Sample 1		Sample 2	
	Mean weight (%)	Standard Deviation	Mean weight (%)	Standard Deviation
FeO	66.28	0.27	68.76	0.34
Al ₂ O ₃	7.26	0.79	7.67	0.53
MgO	-	-	-	-
SiO ₂	21.39	0.60	21.70	0.13
TiO ₂	0.97	0.10	1.04	0.17
MnO	1.55	0.14	0.05	0.03
P ₂ O ₅	0.82	0.06	0.46	0.09
CaO	1.06	0.11	0.17	0.02
S	0.05	0.07	-	-
V ₂ O ₅	0.11	0.11	0.15	0.18
K ₂ O	0.50	0.02	-	-
Total	99.99	-	100	-

The smiths market their products through middlemen who buy the products in bulk for sale in the markets. However, smiths located in the markets' immediate environments, such as those at Gwangwan, could also sell their wares directly in the market.

STAGES OF IRON WORKING

Field visits were taken to various ancient mining, and smelting sites, as well as to some existing blacksmiths' workshops. It was observed in particular, that the blacksmiths' choice of materials, heat treatment sequences, and shaping and joining operations left some room for improvement if the potentials of iron working in these areas are to be fully realized.

Source of Iron

Throughout a great part of Africa (including Nigeria), there has been, especially in the past, an extensive tree cover to provide fuel, and sizable deposits of ores of iron are also found, extensively in the form of hematite or limonite which are also essential constituents of laterites and other widespread derived or residual rocks. Another source of iron extensively used by primitive smelters is magnetite. Magnetite occurs as a constituent of the river and stream sands in many parts of Africa, and can often be seen, after heavy rain, as a deposit of black sand on the beds of shallow streams. The relative iron content of these ores is: magnetite (Fe₃O₄), 72.4%; hematite (Fe₂O₃), 70%; and limonite, 20-55%.

The iron ore resource of Katsina is mainly a residual ferruginised laterite – a hard compact and sometimes perforated rusty brown rock that occurs in layers, either capping weathered inselbergs or as a layer below the top soil in some laterite pits. Important locations include Makurdi Hills, Dan-ali Hills, Lafiaro and Pauwa. This ferruginised laterite contains the iron mineral limonite. It is, of course, low grade from the mineral content point of view.

Before the introduction of European scrap iron, much of the iron worked by smiths in Katsina and other areas like Kano, were mined and smelted in southern Katsina. Katsina smelters also supplied iron to Sokoto and other places in Hausaland.

The Primitive Furnace and Smelting Operations

As far as can be deduced from archeological evidences, the shaft type of furnace seem to be the earliest, and it is the most widespread in areas of Katsina, Kano and Zaria in particular and in Hausaland in general. The quality of this furnace depends on the kind of earth used, how it was heat-

treated, and how many times it could be used. If it can be used more than one time, then it would be only the tuyeres that would require changing.

The furnace was built of clay mixed with grass. It was usually 2 metres high (figures 1 and 2) and an average man could encircle it with his arms. It has a small hole about half way up through which happenings inside the furnace could be viewed and another hole at the bottom through

Table 3: Hardness values from laboratory tests.

Sample	ROCKWELL HARDNESS (HRV)			AVERAGE HARDNESS (HRV)
	1	2	3	
Unforged	50	49	50	49.67
Chisel (forged item)	98	100	97	98.33
Hoe blade (forged item)	91	85	89	88.33

which the slag ran into a pit. Air is blown into the furnace through openings at a level above the bottom. The space below the air entrance provided a place for the sponge to form, where it would not be exposed to oxygen from air, which otherwise would combine with the reduced iron to form iron oxide

The furnaces were bellows-driven. The bellows consisted of two bladders made from goat skin, with wooden handles fixed to the tops and with wooden tubes leading from the bottom of the bellows into the tuyeres which delivered the air into the furnace.

Conditions prevalent in the shaft furnace were favourable to carbon absorption: high temperatures could be attained and reduction of iron ore began at considerable level above the combustion zone so that any reduced iron would be in contact with hot carbon for a longer time at higher temperatures than say in the pit or hearth type furnaces.

The carbon from charcoal used as fuel, apart from supplying the necessary heat, also provided the chemical agent to reduce the iron from its oxide, protected the reduced iron from being re-oxidized so long as it was surrounded by hot carbon; and could provide alloying material for the reduced iron to form iron-carbon alloys of several types.

These furnaces have the limitations of not being able to attain melting point temperature of iron; excessive heat loss through the walls and top; absence of slag tapping provisions in some of them, which calls for demolition and rebuilding of another furnace whenever the slag pit was filled; cracking of the walls at high temperatures since they have no shields and so stopping the smelting operations to avoid collapse of the furnace; and negligible pre-heating of the air. Figure 1 depicts these primitive furnaces. Table 1 compares the primitive furnace with the modern blast furnace.

Smelting – the reduction of iron ore – takes place at a temperature of about 700°C in the primitive furnace. This temperature is by far below the melting point of iron (1500°C). In the modern industrial blast furnaces, the iron from the ore separates from the slag (and being heavier than the later) runs to the bottom of the furnace from where it is poured into casting moulds to form pig iron while the slag is run off.

The method of producing iron in the primitive furnace is much more complicated than it is in the modern furnace. In the former, iron ore together with a special charcoal (produced from hard wood) were charged into furnace from the top and then the charcoal was lighted. The carbon from the charcoal burns and combines with oxygen from the air to form carbon monoxide. The hot gas passes up through the furnace and reacts with the iron oxide (ore) by removing oxygen from it, forming carbon dioxide and leaving pure chemically deposited iron (bloom). The reduction process actually begins at very low temperature, probably about 450°C [Enozie, 1992]. The reaction equations are:

The iron produced in this process has not melted; it has been chemically deposited in very small quantities which, due to the influence of the higher temperature near the bottom, become soft and adhere to one another or to the slag and unconsumed charcoal to form a loosely coherent mass known as sponge iron.

Figure 1: A drawing of the primitive furnaces on a smelting site.

Impurities in the iron ore, such as silica combined with some of the iron oxide for form a liquid siliceous slag of high iron content, at least part of which permeated the pores of the sponge iron, while the remainder ran out of the furnace bottom opening into the pit.

After a sponge of sufficient size had formed, it was suitable for making tools so the blacksmiths refined it. This was done by reheating the iron with charcoal and repeatedly hammering it so as to express the remaining slag and weld the iron crystals together.

The smelting of iron is a task needing and using up much energy and very much complicated by ritual which, if not properly observed, it was believed, the smelting process would fail.

Bloomery Slags

Bloomery slags in the primitive iron smelting process were once solidified molten silicate matter that resulted from the reduction of iron ore, which was composed of gangue material from the iron ore, fuel ash and refractory materials. When chemically analyzed, slag from smelting operations contain higher proportion of silica than the that from smithing operations. On the other hand, smithing slag has a higher proportion of manganese than did that from smelting [Andah, 1997].

Tap slag was the most prominent in shaft furnace used in Hausaland in bloomery iron smelting. Here the furnace was provided with an aperture for draining the molten slag out of the furnace while the smelting was in progress. The molten slag solidified outside the furnace. Such tap slag was flattish in form with lava-like ripple appearance.

Chemically, the bloomery slag was composed mainly of iron oxide and silicate which together made up over 90% of slag constituent. Iron silicate slag from bloomery iron smelting was generally fayalitic ($2FeO.S_2O_2$) in composition. However, there was slag in which MnO, MnO, or CaO replaced the FeO in the iron silicate to form manganese, magnesium, or calcium silicate respectively. In some other metal working operations such as smithing and forging of blooms in the hearth, as well as the smelting of copper and lead ores, where iron ore was used to flux the smelt, produced fayalitic slag. Table 2

shows the chemical constituents found in various samples of the slag from bloomery iron smelting sites that were analyzed.

Factors upon which slag mineral composition depend were observed to include: ore composition; chemical composition of fuel used; chemical composition of the refractory material used; chemical composition of any flux(es) used; the rate of air blast; the state of the slag as it is removed from the furnace (i.e. whether it was tapped in molten state or removed after solidification in the furnace); and the surrounding conditions of the slag since it was formed.

SMITHING

While the blacksmiths worked mild steel and obtained their raw materials from the local miners and smelters, the whitesmiths – who worked brass, gold, silver, etc – obtained their raw materials mostly from imports from Asia, and Europe. Among this later smiths, tin was the only metal obtained and

Figure 2: Sections through a primitive furnace.

smelted locally up to 1913 [Enozie, 1992]. On the other hand, blacksmithing is the one considered to be wholly indigenous before the eighteenth century.

Though blacksmithing is an ancient craft whose forging techniques is the progenitor of the various metal-forming operations in use today, the process among the local people still remains primitive and rudimentary that it is hardly employed as a viable means of commercial production of metal ware.

The various operations undertaken by the local blacksmiths include the following:

Heating: in which the work piece is buried in a mass of charcoal at the exhaust of the bellows in the hearth and then heated to cherry-red hotness – corresponding to temperatures in the austenite range – and held there for about 20 to 30 minutes.

Forging: in which the heated piece is hammered, punched or chiseled into a desired shape.

Casting: which is carried out only by the whitesmiths as the blacksmith is unable to reach sufficient temperatures to melt the steel in the hearth, whereas the whitesmith's metals have lower melting temperatures and is able to cast metals.

In the open mould method, the molten metal was poured into an open mould and allowed to solidify, after which the solid metal was hammered to strain-harden and then heated and bent to shape. This was mostly utilized to produce bangles. In the lost wax method, a model of the object was made and was then covered with clay mixed with termite earth. This was then baked, whereupon the wax ran out of the mould and leaving it exactly of the desired shape. The casting was then made by pouring the molten metal into the baked mould. After cooling, the mould was broken, leaving the casting intact.

Mixing the clay with termite earth made the clay more focused, thereby helping in eliminating cavity defects. This method has been revived in the last century in the casting of gas turbine blades.

Tempering: for tools like the chisels in which only the cutting parts need hardening, the blacksmiths heat the tool to cherry-red hotness, and quenching only the cutting edge. The cooled end was then cleaned and the heat from the shank of the tool was allowed to temper the cutting edge to the correct colour, after which the whole tool was quenched.

Normalizing: here, the blacksmith heated the steel to red hotness and soaked it for sometime – depending on the thickness of the article – in a medium such as water or oil. It was then allowed to cool in air. A softer material was obtained in the end.

Joining: metals were joined by the smiths by brazing and welding. In brazing (and soldering), the two surfaces to be joined were held in place over fire and finely ground pieces of bottle glass (which acted as flux) was spread over the surfaces. A piece of brass (solder) was then placed at the top and heated until it melted and spread onto the spaces between the surfaces. A strong joint was formed after cooling.

Plate 1A: Unforged Sample (Normalized Structure)

Plate 1B: Forged Sample (From a hoe blade)

Plate 1C: Forged Sample (from a quenched chisel cutting edge)

In welding, the parts to be joined were immersed in wet clay sand (flux) and heated to cherry-red hotness and then the hot pieces were hammered to unite the surfaces over an anvil. The flux combined with the iron oxide produced by heating to high temperature and formed a fusible slag which was scattered by the hammer blows.

Quenching: the local blacksmiths largely employed water as a quenching medium. Though rarely, they also used groundnut oil especially where the degree of hardness required was not appreciable.

LABORATORY TESTS

One sample each from the blacksmiths forge item and from the unforged material (the blacksmith's input material) was laboratory-tested at the Materials Science Laboratory, Mechanical Engineering Department, Bayero University, Kano, Nigeria. May, 1995.

The forged sample was sectioned, ground flat and rough-polished on glycerol-lubricated silicon carbide paper. The grinding and polishing were done very slowly to avoid heating and oxidation, the depth of grinding and polishing being sufficient to eliminate damage arising from specimen preparation. The sample from the unforged material was also similarly prepared for testing.

The harness test was conducted on the samples using only the Rockwell B-scale, as the deformation and heat-treatment employed by the blacksmith was not expected to yield higher hardness in the mild steel he employed.

For the microstructure observations, the fine-polished and etched specimens were mounted on the metallurgical microscope and the observed images were sketched. The etching reagent used was 2% nitric acid-methyl alcohol. Test results are shown in Table 3 and in Appendix A.

DECLINE OF THE INDIGENOUS IRON INDUSTRY

No doubt, the coming into contact with Europeans contributed significantly to the decline of the iron smelting in Katsina. As some of the blacksmiths interviewed put it, that though tools made from locally smelted iron were stronger than those made from imported iron – obtained in forms of rods and bars from iron containers of paints, engine oil, corrugated iron sheets, etc – they preferred the imported iron because it was easy to work, cheap to buy and readily available. Among the factors that contributed to the decline include the following:

The British Conquest

Immediately after the conquest of Katsina emirate in 1900 by the British, the later prohibited the bearing and production weapons. This effectively cut the potential of the blacksmith by more than half since the society for which he worked was war-faring and mainly agrarian.

Further, in 1902, the British enacted a lands proclamation edict number thirteen [Mukhtar, 1990] which vested ownership of all lands and the resources therein in the hands of Britain, which also regulates the utilization of the land and its resources. The edict deprived the entire people of the area the ownership of any unoccupied and uncultivated lands and also deprived them access to any minerals from the lands. This contributed immensely to the collapse of indigenous mining and smelting. For example, in 1925 [Mukhtar, 1990] in Pauwa, the colonial state not only made all independent mining illegal, but also closed down eighteen local iron smelting furnaces. The colonialists also established forest reserves where no wood was obtained for any purpose as well as taxing of the trees used in places not reserved. This made it further difficult for local smelting which depended largely on wood fuel, i.e. even if the smelting could be done illegally.

The creation of boundaries by the British constituted barriers to population movements, interactions, trade and exchange of ideas and skills. Thus, trade between communities collapsed and so did the seasonal migration to the centres of iron mining and smelting. This was further aided by the imposition of discriminatory custom duties against local resources and products. These duties favoured European products whose markets gradually replaced those of their indigenous counterparts.

The British, by its imports policy, flooded the markets with European scraps and manufactured goods. The supply and distribution of these to all areas in northern Nigeria were greatly increased after 1911 when the railway reached Zaria and Kano. This further contributed to the decline in local iron production. It is probable that by the end of the 1930's, locally mined iron had been replaced almost completely by the imported scrap metal [Gregory, 1972].

Considering the poor economic status of the miners, smelters and blacksmiths, imported iron was not cheap by any standard. This, coupled with the special tax imposed on blacksmiths, forced many of them to abandon the craft for other professions. The few that held on to the craft resorted to securing metal supplies from the railways in Kano and Zaria. Consequently, theft of railway iron became rampant.

Lastly, the maintenance of the emir's palace and the central prison – a responsibility assigned to the city blacksmiths under the direction of the "Chief of Blacksmiths" – was taken over by the then newly established public works department. These artisans thus lost their function and importance. The result of all these factors was the stagnation and deterioration of the techniques and skills involved in the industry, leading finally to its collapse.

Other Factors

1. *Importation of Firearms*: One of the early salient factors for the decline of iron working is the importation of firearms. During the last decade of the nineteenth century, imported firearms became generally available in northern Nigeria. Thus, the market for the locally made ones by the blacksmiths

rapidly declined as they were forced to abandon the making of such items as paddled amour, spears and swords mostly used for defence and hunting.

2. *Lack of Planned Apprenticeship*: Apprenticeship was very informal: no binding contract; no payment of fees involved; and no fixed apprenticeship duration. So the apprentice may come and go as he pleases and may pay little or no attention to the craft. The long-term impact of this is that the art would be poorly transmitted from generation to generation.

3. *Lack of Research Culture*: No body – not even the artisans themselves – engaged in research in this area to seek to improve the quality of their work. Thus, no one sought to know why things happened the way they do; certainly, curiosity about certain aspects of their work would have enlightened them on not only how things happened and so improve on their work and products, but also pave way for future developments.

4 *Conservatism*: The artisans were not willing to be introduced to new technological innovations, even if those things meant improving on the primitive methods. The attitude was one of “whatever was good for our ancestors is also good for us”. For example, they used charcoal from ‘Kirya’ tree (*Pro Sopic Africa*) which was scarce and obtained from long distances, when coke was more available and effective and could have been used.

5. *Lack of Encouragement/Government Assistance*: Because these artisans largely depended for their means of livelihood more on farming than on the art of iron working, their key functions, importance and value to themselves and to the society were eclipsed. They ought to have been encouraged by government, both financially and by way of easy access to the resources they used. These would have boosted their production capacity.

6. *Change of Attitude*: Because of the poor economic status of the smiths and smelters, the later generations of young men were less interested in these arts and would rather look for jobs with better prospect of pay.

7. *No Formation of Guilds*: In the words of [Yusuf, 1996], “generally, in the whole of Hausaland, there was the lack of highly developed and regular cooperation between the artisans in the conventional guild. Instead, we had a situation in which each of the separated clusters of blacksmiths was essentially autonomous, with the individual smiths of each group organizing their work quite independently of each other, and setting their own prices and standards of production”. This limited the transfer of skills between artisans and this further retarded the progress of the craft.

In the equivalent European industry, it is instructive to note that, in addition to the machinery, a most decisive factor in the growth of the industry was the change-over from domestic production to the factory system, with the guild making the intermediate stage.

DISCUSSION

The austenite phase change is the most critical in the diversification of mechanical properties of steel in the sense that every equilibrium phase transformation has to pass through this phase. The measure, therefore, of the adequacy of the blacksmith’s heat treatment depends largely on whether or not the austenite region was attained. If it is then air-cooled, the product should reveal fine-pearlite structure.

Temperature

A comparison of plate 1A with other plates (1B, and 1C) reveals that the equilibrium (pearlite) phase transformation occurred in the forged samples – indicating the austenite phase change. Hence, the blacksmith’s operations are viable as a means of imparting versatile micro-structures and therefore mechanical properties of the steel.

Degree of Deformation

This is limited by human strength, as well as by the blacksmith’s disinclination to go to higher temperatures such as yellow-white hotness or to re-heat the job frequently between forging blows. However, remarkable extents of deformation were achieved in some cases, such as when a digger or a

hoe is flattened from 2-inch round bar to a bladed end only 1/8 as thick as the original thickness. This represents a very severe deformation. Matchets, sickles, axes and hoes, unless they are made from coils (strips), which are not yet made locally, represent even more severe deformations. Thus, the blacksmith's operations are adequate in this regard. The degree of deformation gives rise to the significant alteration of mechanical properties evident in Table 3.

Mechanical Properties

The result of hardness test and the micro-structure details are shown in Table 3 and on Plates 1A, 1B and 1C, respectively. The hardness is seen to be higher in the forged samples than in the unforged samples. This means that the tensile strength is also higher in the forged samples. Since ductility decreases with increasing hardness, it can be said that the ductility of the forged samples would be lower compared to the unforged material. The high strength is significant and is in agreement with expectation.

The martensite structure observed in plate 1C indicates that the sample was quenched and further confirms that austenite will be obtained without the materials being heated to the austenite range. The clear resolution of pearlite in these structures indicates that equilibrated plain carbon steels.

The microstructure results in plates 1A to 1C all point to a probable composition of the beginning of material – mild steel. Remarkable directional property was also achieved where the grains were observed to elongate in the direction of forging. This directionality is parallel to the force that will be applied to the tool in its working life, which means longer life for the tool.

Uniformity of Deformation

In blacksmithing, deformation of material is very severe and it is seldom uniform over the entire forged zone. This is evident in the significant scatter of the data in Table 3. It was observed that the blacksmith's forging blows are far from uniformity in the hot zone. The piece is usually turned over in between blows delivered by a hammer. More often than not, the job is done by one man for better coordination; the job is held in one hand and the hammer in the other hand. Generally, only five to ten blows are delivered before the piece cools and hardens. The severe deformation imparted after the workpiece has cooled below the annealing temperature range only serve to produce severe work-hardening. The result is patchy surface finish and inhomogeneous internal deformation, leading to inhomogeneity in mechanical properties.

Such inhomogeneous deformation of steel, couple with the normalizing treatment (air-cooling) and failure to perform follow-up anneal, means a good deal of residual stresses in the product. The worsened by the fact that only few implements are heated and forged all over; in most cases only the working end (blade edge) is heated and forged. Thus, severe variation in structure and properties exist over the implement. The result does not only impair mechanical properties, but also makes the implement prone to corrosion. This limits long-term use, particularly in sea water or in salt-laden air of coastal and tropical areas. Inhomogeneity of structure and properties in blacksmith's products is probably the greatest shortcoming in the work of the blacksmiths.

Starting Material

The blacksmith's choice of a starting material is predicated upon convenience, availability and ease of hot-deformation. He comes up with mild, plain carbon steel. This is an excellent choice from the standpoint of versatility in the development of structure and property as discussed above. He could easily generate a great variety in the mechanical properties, hence applications of his products using this starting material; if only he understood the power of heat treatment in materials.

The hardness and strength required in the blacksmith's products are not so high as to necessitate going to alloy or tool steels for the mean time. However, corrosion resistance and aesthetic appeal might become important factors; in that case, plain carbon steels would no longer be adequate. It is unlikely, however, that a blacksmith untutored in the science of metal alloying could master the intricacies of delicate phase balance needed in working with such alloys as stainless steels.

General Discussion

An attempt has been made here to present an account of local iron working processes as accurately as possible. Until quite recently, and even now, properly recorded processes could probably be counted on

the fingers of one's hand. Different versions of the iron smelting processes were given by different smiths interviewed. There are many references to iron-smelting in journals concerned with iron and anthropology, but very often, the accounts are clearly inaccurate in certain respects, and it then becomes difficult to place any reliability on them. A common mistake is to describe how the iron melts and runs into a lump at the bottom of the furnace into moulds which are placed around the furnace. In truth, the iron never melts in primitive furnace; if it did, it then would have formed cast iron, which would be useless to a smith because he would be unable to work it by the methods at his disposal.

The very few remaining smiths still practicing here today possess still possess the artifice, skill and talent, although most of them are illiterates with regard to western education which would have helped them in improving their artifice.

RECOMMENDATION

The main aim of this work has been to study the processes employed in iron working in Katsina state right from the iron ore mining to smelting and through to blacksmithing stages; to compare these processes with the modern methods; to give the processes some scientific explanation; and to suggest ways by which some of the processes still being practiced from the old ways can be improved upon. Some of the suggested improvements considered fundamental are given below.

Temperature Measuring Techniques: The major essence of heat-treatment is to alter the properties of a material and this can be achieved largely by control of temperature in the heating process, time for soaking, and the cooling speed. There is therefore the need to know the temperatures attained during heating. Bearing in mind that the local smiths cannot read temperature-measuring instruments like the thermometer, a more practical way to guide them on temperature estimations is needed. Thus, such methods suggested include:

Indicating paints and crayons (for small-scale heat-treatment): which change colour or appearance at given temperature ranges. Hence, the paint or crayon could be used to make a mark on the workpiece. Temper Colours: when a quenched steel is heated, it changes colour which is dependent on the temperature reached. This method is similar to the first one; so all the smiths need do is to drop a quenched steel in the hearth and observe the colour it turns to have an idea of the temperature attained. This method would be applicable to only steel and no other metal.

Carburizing: A method of carburizing is to grind charcoal and using this to cover the workpiece in a casing (whose material can withstand the carburizing temperatures) and then heating to the carburizing temperature. The blacksmiths could be taught this simple method.

Casting: In small casting small items like plates and rings the blacksmiths use the lost wax method. In this process, the wax extension above the wax ring acts as a riser and therefore there are no problems of shrinkage. However, for bigger castings, the blacksmith needs to be told to provide a riser to compensate the shrinkage effects.

Quenching methods: To minimize distortions, the blacksmith needs to know that long cylindrical articles need to be quenched vertically; flat section edge-wise; and that thick ends should enter the bath first.

Eliminating soft spots: to prevent steam bubbles forming soft spots, the quenching bath should be agitated. In other words, components should be shaken well in the medium during quenching.

Forging: this should be carried out by a simple mechanical press so as to have uniformity in the deformation or by using a simple drop forging mechanism, in order to save effort.

Quenching media: the two media that the smiths are familiar with are water and groundnut oil. He needs to be taught that some modifications like adding salt to the water or warming the water will alter the cooling speed of the medium. The oils could be extended to include mineral, animal and plant oils, each of which has different cooling speed.

Furnace: improvements in furnace design should be based on the limitations discussed earlier. The blowers, for example, may replace the bellows in the smiths forge so as to reduce the effort.

CONCLUSION

The technical aspects of the smelting and smithing processes were discussed right from the mining of the ore, through smelting to the smithing stages. The smith's methods of hot-working, degrees of deformation, and casting methods among others were also critically analyzed and suggestions were put forward. For sound uniform and versatile development of microstructures and mechanical properties in the entire products it is very necessary for the smith to adopt a structural approach to pre- and post-fabrication heat treatment. For this, the smiths need some scientific knowledge of the behaviours of metals and alloys.

In view of the foregoing study, metallurgical industries that exist today are only remnants of the viable, sound and developing industries of the pre-colonial period. We have also seen how and why the industries declined and the point in time this declination began. Also, a concrete basis for development could be established on a foundation of viable indigenous industries and technology. The professional experience and spirit of excellence of this practice could be used to assist in laying that foundation. The past is gone and cannot be retrieved or revived but its spirit and experience can be borrowed to transform our present situation.

REFERENCE

Andah, B. W. (1997) 'The Epistemology of West African Settlements'. West African Journal of Archeology, University of Nigeria, Nsukka. Pp 32 – 51.

Enozie, F. (1992) 'Early Iron Technology in Igboland'. West African Journal of Archeology, University of Nigeria, Nsukka. Pp 88.

Gregory, C. E. (1972) 'A Concise History of Mining'. Pergaman.

Mukhtar, M. (1990) 'The Decline and Collapse of Indigenous Iron Industries in Northern Nigeria, 1903 – 1989 AD'. Smelting and Smithing, Kano, February, 1990.

Okafor, E. E. (1997) 'Early Iron Smelting in Africa'. West African Journal of Archeology, University of Nigeria, Nsukka. Pp 83 – 97.

Terkel, R. 'Principles of Extractive Metallurgy'. McGraw-Hill Book Company, London. 1983.

Yusuf, J. K. (1996) 'Bi-annual Historical and Cultural Magazine'. History and Culture Bureau, Katsina. Pp 26 – 36.

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